

EFFECTS OF PERFUME ON THE HUMAN BODY

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Annotation: *This article provides information on aromatherapy, the effect of perfume smells on human health and mood, classification of smells depending on their effect on the human body.*

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From time immemorial, aromatherapy has been used to treat many ailments and increase overall vitality. With the help of essential oils got rid of various diseases. Hippocrates, Galen, and other well-known healers have resorted to such methods. Since the 1980s, the study of how new odors affect physiology and health has been developing in the field of aromatherapy.

Smells are related to our memories and emotions. With the help of this or that odor, chemical processes begin in the human brain. It in turn commands the production of certain substances and hormones throughout the body. Therefore, with the help of odors can change the state of the nervous system and the biochemical composition of organs. The science of aromatherapy is based on this “smell-reaction” chain. In this regard, one should choose fragrant oils very carefully. Because choosing the “wrong” scent can have a negative impact on a person’s body, mood, or psychological state.

At present, the treatment of diseases using plant odors is carried out by Professor of Baku Health Hasanov Hasanov Sh.G. is carried out on the basis of the method developed by. In this way, using the original scents of bay, rosemary, geranium, they carry out treatment and achieve good results. Essential oils extracted from bay, rosemary, geranium are useful for the body, especially for diseases of the cardiovascular system, various neuroses, insomnia. The results of

the treatment showed that the smells have a strong effect on the body's adaptive forces and their importance in maintaining human health.

Every smell affects a person to a certain extent. This action occurs, on the one hand, by direct physiological effects on the body, and, on the other hand, by the associations they cause. For example, some odors irritate the nervous system, while others are calming. In general, odors can be divided into three conditional groups: pleasant, unpleasant, and indifferent.

Pleasant scent - we want to smell for as long as possible. It gives us pleasure. But there are a lot of pleasant smells for some and unpleasant smells for others. Most often, some like the smell of tar, others like the smell of camphor or onion, garlic, anchovies and cheese, the smell of hydrogen sulfide in cabbage.

The smell of cheeses and some other similar products given in other perfume mixes is considered "unpleasant". For example, the rotten smell of Roquefort cheeses produced in France is considered unpleasant. Not only is the smell of accepted musk considered unpleasant, but among many people and peoples it is considered pleasant. Many, for example, do not tolerate the smell of roses. Thus, the psychological definition of odor quality is very relative.

Indifferent odors are odors we don't notice. We became so used to them that we stopped feeling them. For example, the smell of ordinary air, home, perfume. Sometimes the notion of indifference is so great that it is possible to remain indifferent even to the over-saturated air of laboratories.

The nose is a very delicate instrument. The mucous layer that covers it is one of the most sensitive areas of the body. Odor receptors are associated with the nervous system. When fragrant substances are inhaled, the irritating energy of the receptors is converted into nerve excitation energy that is transmitted to the central nervous system via nerve fibers. The brain begins to respond synchronously to the impulses of the most sensitive receptors, and through it the whole body is affected. Impulses coming to the organs through the nerve fibers change the state of these

organs, exciting, intensifying or weakening their activity. The biological activity of the body and its protection changes.

The role of fragrances in nature is enormous. Vapors of essential oils emitted by leaves or flowers surround them on all sides. Leaves from overheating during the day and cooling at night, as well as in dry weather

Currently, synthetic fragrances of musk are used in the development of perfumes. They form the basis of a collection of perfumes with many new scents for men and women. These indicators should be taken into account when choosing perfumes. In this way we can prevent or treat diseases.

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